

№2

2023 | АПРЕЛЬ

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

НАУЧНЫЙ ВЕСТНИК
SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN

ISSN: 2181-4554
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4554

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-2

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР

АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

I-ЖИЛД, 2-СОН

BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-2

ТОШКЕНТ – 2023

Бош муҳаррир:

Бахриддинов О. – юридик фанлар номзоди, доцент

Масъул муҳаррир:

Ахмедов Р. – социология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори

Таҳририят аъзолари:

Эгамбердиева А. – психология фанлари номзоди, доценти
Мирзабеков Ғ. – педагогика фанлари номзоди, доценти
Гафуров У. – иқтисод фанлари доктори, профессор
Насиров Р. – тарих фанлари доктори, профессори
Фозилов У. – юридик фанлар номзоди, доцент
Пўлатова Д. – фалсафа фанлари номзоди, доцент
Якубов И. – сиёсий фанлар номзоди, доцент
Азизов У. – социология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори
Матчанов А. – биология фанлари доктори, профессор
Зайтов А. – физика-математика фанлари доктори, профессор
Гафурова Д. – кимё фанлар доктори, доцент
Касимов И. – тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Марипова С. – геология-минерология фанлари номзоди
Каримова С. – фармацевтика фанлари номзоди, доцент
Матёқубова Т. – филология фанлари номзоди, доцент
Қодирова С. – санъатшунослик фанлари доктори, профессор
Сатторов З. – техника фанлари номзоди, профессор
Шодманов М. – қишлоқ хўжалиги фанлари номзоди, доцент
Сафарова Н. – география фанлари номзоди, доцент
Мустаев Б. – архитектура фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори
Якубжонова Ш. – география фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори

Мазкур илмий-амалий ва таҳлилий-қийосий ахборотнома Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Администрацияси ҳузуридаги Ахборот ва оммавий коммуникациялар агентлиги томонидан 2023 йил 24 февраль куни № 065358-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Page Maker\Верстка\Саҳифаловчи: Абдураҳмон Хасанов

Таҳририят манзили: <https://imfaktor.uz>, 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2/27-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55, E-mail: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

© IMFAKTOR Pages, 2023 йил.

© Муаллифлар жамоаси, 2023 йил.

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES

Филология фанлари

YAKUBJONOVA Janona
Ferghana State university
Student

XOLDORVA Hilola
Ferghana State university
Scientific supervisor
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7871756>

LANGUAGE PHRASE AS AN ELEMENT OF SPEECH ETIQUETTE

ANNOTATION

This article demonstrates the modern development of teaching speech etiquette (SE) and describes the importance of using activities to improve speech competence. In the present work the author develops a system of activities and exercises consisting of a complex or series of exercises aimed at mastering the linguoculturological features of the speech etiquette (SE) within the framework of a culture of communicative behavior. However, there is still necessity of improving language and speech competence as well as the culture of communication.

Keywords: speech etiquette (SE), linguoculturology, activity, exercise, communication, culture.

TIL IBORASI, NUTQ ODOBI ELEMENTI SIFATIDA

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola nutq odob-axloq qoidalarini (SE) o'qitishning zamonaviy rivojlanishini namoyish etadi va nutq kompetensiyasini yaxshilash uchun faoliyatdan foydalanish muhimligini tavsiflaydi. Ushbu asarda muallif rivojlanadi kommunikativ xulq-atvor madaniyati doirasida nutq odob-axloqining (SE) lingvokulturologik xususiyatlarini o'zlashtirishga qaratilgan kompleks yoki bir qator mashqlardan iborat faoliyat va mashqlar tizimi. Biroq, til va nutq qobiliyatini, shuningdek, muloqot madaniyatini yaxshilash zarurati hali ham mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq odobi (SE), lingvokulturologiya, faoliyat, mashq, muloqot, madaniyat.

ЯЗЫКОВАЯ ФРАЗА КАК ЭЛЕМЕНТ РЕЧЕВОЙ ЭТИКЕТ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье демонстрируется современное развитие обучения речевому этикету (SE) и описывается важность использования видов деятельности для повышения речевой компетентности. В настоящей работе автор развивает система мероприятий и упражнений, состоящая из комплекса или серии упражнений, направленных на овладение лингвокультурологическими особенностями речевого этикета (SE) в рамках культуры коммуникативного поведения. Однако по-прежнему существует необходимость в совершенствовании языковой и речевой компетентности, а также культуры общения.

Ключевые слова: речевой этикет (SE), лингвокультурология, деятельность, упражнение, общение, культура.

Speech is so familiar a feature of daily life that we rarely pause to define it. It seems as natural to man as walking, and only less so than breathing. Yet it needs but a moment's reflection to convince us that this naturalness of speech is but an illusory feeling. The process of acquiring speech is, in sober fact, an utterly different sort of thing from the process of learning to walk. In the case of the latter function, culture, in other words, the traditional body of social usage, is not seriously brought into play.

The child is individually equipped, by the complex set of factors that we term biological heredity, to make all the needed muscular and nervous adjustments that result in walking. Indeed, the very conformation of these muscles and of the appropriate parts of the nervous system may be said to be primarily adapted to the movements made in walking and in similar activities. In a very real sense the normal human being is predestined to walk, not because his elders will assist him to learn the art, but because his organism is prepared from birth, or even from the moment of conception, to take on all those expenditures of nervous energy and all those muscular adaptations that result in walking. To put it concisely, walking is an inherent, biological function of man.

In the century of technological process, more opportunities and necessity for the institutions of relations with different countries, in all places that the role of English because the leading means that of intercultural communication is speedily increasing, the importance of eliminating and enhancing imperfections within the method of making effective strategies of teaching English ought to be greatly highlighted.

The technology of teaching speech etiquette (SE) involves the definition of a system of exercises. The system of exercises can be defined as organized and interdependent actions of students aimed at achieving a specific educational goal in the formation of skills. It should have certain characteristics (scientific, interdependent; sequence and accessibility; repeatability of speech actions and language material; communicative orientation), but in the absence of at least one of them, the system turns into a complex or series. In the present work, we tried to show a system of exercises consisting of a complex or series of exercises aimed at mastering the linguocultural features of the SE within the framework of a culture of communicative behavior. Recently, the opinion has been firmly established that it is necessary to train students of FL in those conditions in which speech activity really functions. "Any activity can be learned by performing this activity", in speech conditions with the help of "activity means and technology of working with them". In this case, Passov under the means of activity means exercises. Belyaev also recognizes foreign language practice as a decisive factor in education. We agree with this opinion that one can only master speech activity by performing the appropriate actions: speak, speak, listen, listen, read and read. According to Passov, lessons only in material can be lexical, grammatical, and in spirit they should be speech, so in the proposed new concept of foreign language education he outlined only conditional speech and speech exercises. The author notes that in communication technology all the exercises used should be speech, and conditionally-speech exercises are used to create conditions for the formation of skills.

We believe that language exercises should not be present as part of conditional speech exercises, but separately. It is necessary to take into account the teachings of L.V. Shcherba on three aspects of linguistic phenomena (Shcherba, 1974:26) and the types of exercises indicated by Bukhbinder: information (knowledge), operational (skills) and motivational (skills). Based on this, we take as a basis the classification of Bukhbinder, informational for presenting linguistic and linguocultural knowledge of SE in contacting cultures, operational and motivational exercises should contribute to mastering SE in various communication situations and the speech itself to enter the "dialogue of cultures". Therefore, it is advisable to use these two types the exercises. Taking into account all above mentioned and based on the parameters of the exercises and the conditions for their use, the training of use will be based on the following classification of exercises: informational, operational and motivational.

REFERENCES

1. Bayburin, A.K. (1981). The ritual in the system of symbolic means of culture//Ethnolinguistic functions of culture. Leningrad: Science. pp. 23-42.
2. Fomenko, Yu.V. (1990). Language and speech. Tutorial. Novosibirsk: NGPI. pp. 79.
3. Galskova, N.D., Gez N.I. (2007). Theory of teaching foreign languages. Linguodidactics and methods. 4th ed. Moscow., Academy. 336 p.
4. Likhachev, D.S. (1994). Culture as a holistic environment//New World. Moscow. №8. p.3-8.
5. Lomtev, T.P. (1976). Language and Speech/In: General and Russian Linguistics. Selected works. Under. ed. T.P. Lomteva. Moscow: Russian language. pp.58-72.
6. Luria, A.R. (1978). General Psychology. Moscow: Pedagogy. 259 p.
7. Sepir, E. (1993). The position of linguistics as a science / In the book: Zvegintsev V.A.
8. The history of linguistics of the XIX-XX centuries in essays and sayings. Part 2. Moscow., Nauka. Pp. 177-185.

ISSN: 2181-4554
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4554

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

I-ЖИЛД, 2-СОН

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ
ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-2

BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES
VOLUME-I, ISSUE-2

“Замонавий тадқиқотлар ахборотномаси” электрон журнали 2023 йил 24 февраль куни № 065358-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

Таҳририят манзили: 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55

Эл. почта: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz